

Evaluación de parámetros fisicoquímicos y toxicológicos para el cálculo del IRCA en los sistemas de abastecimiento de agua potable en zonas rurales de Bogotá, D.C.

Assessment of physicochemical and toxicological parameters influencing the water quality risk index for human consumption (IRCA) in rural drinking water supply systems of Bogotá D.C.

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Resumen

Este estudio se centra en la evaluación de los parámetros fisicoquímicos y toxicológicos que influyen en el comportamiento del Índice de Riesgo de la Calidad del Agua para Consumo Humano (IRCA) en los sistemas de abastecimiento de agua potable de la zona rural de la ciudad de Bogotá D. C., en cumplimiento de la Resolución 2115 de 2007. Para ello, se realizaron comparaciones de los promedios mensuales de los parámetros analizados y del IRCA durante el periodo comprendido entre 2020 y 2023, con el fin de identificar tendencias o patrones de comportamiento. Adicionalmente, se desarrolló un modelado del IRCA, considerándolo como una variable dependiente con una función de distribución de probabilidad continua Beta inflada a cero. Para este análisis se plantearon dos escenarios: uno que incluyó la totalidad de los datos disponibles y otro que consideró únicamente aquellos registros con valores de IRCA iguales o superiores al 14,1 %, correspondientes a niveles de riesgo medio o superiores. En el primer escenario, los parámetros con mayor influencia fueron la conductividad, el pH, el color aparente, el cloro residual libre, el manganeso y la dureza; mientras que en el segundo escenario se identificaron como más influyentes la conductividad, el color, la alcalinidad, los cloruros y la dureza. Asimismo, se identificaron y georreferenciaron zonas con actividades antrópicas, como cultivos cercanos a los puntos de captación de los sistemas de abastecimiento, lo que sugiere una posible contaminación de las fuentes asociada a estas prácticas. En conjunto, los resultados obtenidos buscan aportar insumos técnicos para el fortalecimiento de políticas públicas, en particular la Resolución 622 de 2020, que establece los parámetros a monitorear en la calidad del agua de los sistemas de abastecimiento en zonas rurales.

Palabras clave: IRCA, parámetros fisicoquímicos, parámetros toxicológicos, función de distribución Beta inflada a cero.

Abstract

This study focuses on the assessment of physicochemical and toxicological parameters that influence the behavior of the Water Quality Risk Index for Human Consumption (IRCA) in drinking water supply systems located in rural areas of Bogotá D.C., in compliance with Resolution 2115 of 2007. Monthly average values of the analyzed parameters and the IRCA were compared for the period between 2020 and 2023 to identify trends or behavioral patterns. Additionally, statistical modeling of the IRCA was developed, considering it as a dependent variable following a zero-inflated Beta continuous probability distribution. Two scenarios were evaluated: one including the complete dataset and another considering only records with IRCA values equal to or greater than 14.1%, corresponding to medium risk levels and above. In the first scenario, the parameters with the greatest influence were conductivity, pH, apparent color, free residual chlorine, manganese, and hardness, whereas in the second scenario, conductivity, color, alkalinity, chlorides, and hardness were identified as the most influential variables. Furthermore, areas with anthropogenic activities, such as agricultural practices located near water intake points of the supply systems, were identified and georeferenced, suggesting potential contamination of water sources associated with these activities. Overall, the findings aim to provide technical inputs to support the strengthening of public policies, particularly Resolution 622 of 2020, which establishes the parameters to be monitored for drinking water quality in rural water supply systems.

Keywords: IRCA, physicochemical parameters, toxicological parameters, Beta inflated at zero distribution function.

Introduction

The provision of potable water in rural areas of Colombia poses a significant challenge due to its direct impact on people's health and its broad economic and social effects. Approximately 3 million Colombians living in rural areas lack access to basic potable water services (Moreno, 2020). This issue is part of a broader global crisis; according to the World Bank (2023), around 2 billion people worldwide lack access to safe drinking water, with significantly lower coverage in rural areas. In Colombia, potable water coverage is considerably high in urban areas but much lower in rural regions, with only 359 municipalities achieving water coverage of 15% or less (Superintendencia de Servicios Públicos Domiciliarios de Colombia, 2021). Water scarcity is a critical problem, particularly affecting rural communities where access to clean drinking water is limited. The stark disparities in water supply coverage between urban and rural areas highlight the urgent need for robust regulatory measures to improve water management (Sánchez & Quiroga, 2020).

Drinking water must comply with the physical, chemical, and microbiological standards set by current regulations, as defined in Resolution 2115 of 2007, to ensure its consumption poses no health risks (Ministerio de Salud de Colombia, 2015). It must be transparent, colorless, tasteless, and free of suspended solids. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6 seeks to ensure clean water and sanitation for all, particularly in rural areas where access to potable water is limited (World Bank, 2023).

The development of regulations governing water quality standards and monitoring strategies has been an ongoing process in Colombia, evolving to address emerging challenges related to drinking water safety and public health. Within this regulatory framework, water quality assessment for human consumption is conducted through the Water Quality Risk Index for Human Consumption (IRCA), a composite indicator calculated based on physicochemical, microbiological, and toxicological parameters, which allows the classification of water supply systems according to defined risk levels. The enactment of Resolution 622 in 2020 introduced updates to surveillance protocols

and rural water quality monitoring, specifying the parameters to be analyzed and their monitoring frequencies. This regulatory approach reflects a growing awareness of the complex and multifactorial nature of water quality management, particularly in rural drinking water supply systems (Ministerio de Protección Social de Colombia, 2007; Superintendencia de Servicios Públicos Domiciliarios de Colombia, 2020).

Platforms such as the Drinking Water Quality Surveillance System (SIVICAP) provide a comprehensive framework for health authorities to monitor key water quality parameters, enabling policymakers to effectively assess risks and ensure compliance with established standards, thereby protecting public health (Comisión de Regulación de Agua Potable y Saneamiento Básico, 1994).

Various studies have documented the challenges associated with water quality management in rural areas of Colombia, identifying that many municipalities in Boyacá face physicochemical and microbiological issues in potable water, particularly related to the presence of *Escherichia coli*, total coliforms, residual chlorine, and turbidity. These findings underscore the significant public health risks faced by these communities (Rojas, 202; Henao-Rodríguez & Lis-Gutiérrez, 2025).

Community aqueducts in Latin America, with a specific focus on the San Bernardo aqueduct in Ibagué, revealed a lack of community sanctions for non-payment or water waste and weak community participation in aqueduct management, jeopardizing the sustainability of these systems (Murcia & Francel, 2022). Additionally, anthropogenic factors, such as agricultural activities, also influence water quality. For instance, pesticide concentrations pose health risks, and conventional water treatment methods for contaminated water, such as coagulation-flocculation, adsorption, filtration, and sedimentation, entail high operational costs and may cause secondary contamination through sludge formation (Syafudin et al., 2021).

This study aims to contribute to the existing knowledge on water quality management in Colombia by providing a comparative analysis of regulatory frameworks such as Resolution 2115 of 2007 and Resolution 622 of 2020. Understanding the implications of these regulatory changes will

enable policymakers to make informed decisions to address water quality challenges, particularly in rural communities facing disproportionate risks. Exploring the interaction between regulatory frameworks and the application of generated results can aid in formulating local or national policies related to water management in rural areas. This knowledge can always be used for the purpose of protecting public health.

Experimental Design

The study adopted a quantitative research design, initially applying a deductive approach in which the analysis is grounded in a pre-established theoretical or conceptual framework, where concepts are operationalized into variables, and empirical evidence is subsequently collected to evaluate or test the proposed assumptions (Sousa et al., 2007). The analysis focused on numerical data to address specific research questions and support hypothesis validation. Standardized measurement methods were employed to objectively quantify the variables, enabling the application of statistical techniques to obtain precise and reproducible results.

The research followed an experimental analytical approach, considering the characteristics of rural drinking water supply systems as the independent variable to evaluate their influence on physicochemical and toxicological water quality parameters defined within the applicable regulatory framework. This methodological approach allowed for the identification of relationships between variables and the assessment of patterns associated with water quality risk levels. Compliance with national regulations, particularly Resolution 2115 of 2007 and Resolution 622 of 2020, together with systematic data collection procedures, ensured the generation of robust, quantifiable, and generalizable results regarding water quality conditions in rural supply systems.

Data processing and statistical analysis were conducted using Python and RStudio, which facilitated the organization, filtering, and programming of variables, as well as the implementation of analytical routines for real-world datasets (Downey et al., 2002). The analysis included descriptive statistics, such as measures of central tendency and dispersion, in addition to the development of graphs and tables to support clear and structured data visualization.

Furthermore, linear regression analysis was applied as a statistical modeling technique to examine the relationship between independent variables and the dependent variable represented by the IRCA (Álvarez, 1995).

To support the modeling of the IRCA, the Beta distribution function was employed. In probability theory and statistics, this distribution represents a family of continuous probability distributions defined on a finite interval, making it particularly suitable for variables constrained within bounded ranges (González et al., 2014). Its application allowed the representation of diverse distributional profiles associated with water quality indicators, the estimation of tolerance limits without assuming normality, and the incorporation of probabilistic behavior relevant to environmental data analysis. Specifically, zero-inflated Beta models have been used in ecological and environmental studies to handle data with a high proportion of zero values while capturing underlying continuous variation; this approach can enhance interpretability and flexibility compared to traditional methods. In addition, the Beta distribution is widely used within Bayesian inference frameworks, further supporting its suitability for modeling the behavior of the IRCA and highlighting its potential as a methodological contribution for future research in water quality and sanitary risk assessment (Román, 2016; Tang et al., 2023).

Results and Discussion

The study utilized data extracted from the SIVICAP from 2020 to 2023 to conduct a detailed statistical analysis aimed at identifying the main physicochemical and toxicological parameters affecting the IRCA in rural potable water supply systems in Bogotá. A total of 2016 data points from 40 systems were analyzed to evaluate the adequacy of the parameters established in Resolution 622 of 2020 for water quality monitoring. Upon reviewing the data provided by the SIVICAP platform, the monitored water supply systems were identified. According to the conditions established in Resolution 622 of 2020, 40 rural potable water supply systems in Bogotá D.C. were identified, as shown spatially in **Figure 1**.

The analysis revealed an average IRCA of 25.31% overall years, indicating a medium level of risk and highlighting significant challenges in

Figure 1. Georeferenced rural drinking water supply systems in Bogotá D.C. identified from SIVICAP data in accordance with Resolution 622 of 2020

water quality in rural areas. Although IRCA values fluctuated slightly between years, there were no substantial improvements, underscoring the persistent nature of water quality issues and the need for ongoing intervention. Detailed statistics are provided in **Table 1**.

Based on this, for rural systems, the average IRCA over the four years falls within the Medium Risk category, which would indicate water not suitable for human consumption. Although the mode suggests that a value of “0” (No Risk) is the most frequent, it should be noted that the average is highly sensitive to high data points in the variable, as demonstrated by its maximum value (Lahoz-Beltrá, 2019). To provide a more specific analysis, the annual average IRCA graph is shown in **Figure 2**. The IRCA shows a higher level of risk in 2021, although the general trend remains at a medium

Table 1. The summary statistics for the total IRCA data from 2020 to 2023, which reveals an average IRCA of 25.31%, indicating a medium risk level, based on the analysis of 2016 data points

Statistical Parameter	Units	Result
Total Data	data	2016
Average IRCA	%	25.31 Medium Risk
Median IRCA	%	18.63
Mode IRCA	%	0
Standard Deviation IRCA	%	27.93
Minimum IRCA	%	0
Maximum IRCA	%	97.48

Figure 2. Temporal variation of the IRCA, showing a peak in 2021 and the lowest values in 2023, with an overall medium risk level during the analyzed period

risk level throughout all the years analyzed. It is noteworthy that the IRCA reached its lowest point in 2023. The IRCA behavior during this period shows an increase of 15.41% from 2020 to 2021, followed by a decrease of 16.27% in 2022 and 17.78% in 2023 compared to the previous year. This variation may be attributed to the characteristics of the COVID-19 pandemic concerning the socioeconomic aspects of the systems and their management, the amount of water consumed, and the use of meteorological resources and parameters for each year (Valencia et al., 2000).

It’s important to continue with an analysis comparing the parameters used to calculate the index, without generating a correlation analysis, because the IRCA is related to the parameters of proportionality. So, depending on whether the parameter is within the acceptable range or not,

making it a dichotomous or boolean data point (Toro, 2022), it will be weighted or multiplied by the corresponding proportion to generate the index.

Upon examining the individual parameters, the apparent color consistently remained within acceptable limits but occasionally exceeded thresholds, particularly in 2021. Conductivity, while mostly compliant, showed occasional outliers but did not significantly correlate with IRCA trends. Turbidity consistently exceeded acceptable levels, indicating potential issues with raw water quality. Free residual chlorine, crucial for disinfection, often fell below or above the prescribed limits, suggesting challenges in the treatment processes. The presence of outliers each year may be due to the influence of disinfection unit processes, affecting pathogen protection and increasing resource demand (Lozano-Rivas & Lozano, 2015). Other parameters, such as pH, total alkalinity, chlorides, and total hardness, exhibited variable behavior but did not strongly correlate with IRCA trends.

The measurements of the phosphate parameter in 2022 highlighted the importance of continuous monitoring, especially given the impact of anthropogenic activities on water quality. The data behavior for this parameter by year shows that it is important to note that the Public Health Laboratory, which is responsible for conducting analyses in Bogotá, did not perform phosphate analyses for the years 2022 and 2023. Therefore, for the years 2020 and 2021, there are outliers exceeding the limit according to the standard (0.5 mg/L), which underscores the need to review anthropogenic activities near the potable water treatment system. Although phosphates pose a risk to the population, this risk arises from excessive consumption of the component (Bolaños et al., 2017).

Data behaviors by year for each parameter reveal concerning patterns regarding outliers and the average, which is influenced by these outliers, indicating that the distribution is not symmetric (Lahoz-Beltrá, 2019). Although the presence of several outliers exceeding the limit range defined by the standard does not pose a direct health risk to the population, it may impact the facilities and equipment of the distribution systems (Sigler & Bauder 2017; Puerta & Sánchez, 2022).

The annual behavior for the contaminant lead (mg/L) shows compliance with the standard

each year (0.01). Although there are outliers, it is observed that they do not significantly influence the means, which remains close to the medium. While there is an improvement in 2023, with the lowest standard deviation, it is always important to keep these levels low. It is crucial to note that lead is a bioaccumulative component and can cause poisoning and other symptoms even from small amounts consumed (McFarland & Dozier 2004).

The data for organophosphorus pesticides have limited representativeness, as very few data points differ from 0. Additionally, the standard does not establish limits for this parameter, and it does not show any influence on the IRCA, at least as observed graphically. It is important to remember that organophosphates, derived from pesticides, are compounds that present acute toxic effects and are therefore very dangerous to the health of those who consume them (García de Llasera et al., 2000).

For the generation of the model, although not for predictive purposes, a correlation analysis was performed between the parameters using the obtained data, and this analysis is presented graphically, as shown in **Figure 3**. Theoretically, there is a relationship between the color parameter and the parameters of pH, turbidity, iron, and manganese, although the iron parameter shows the strongest positive relationship, though not significant. There are also theoretically related variables, as indicated in **Figure 4**, which show a similar relationship between chlorides and conductivity, and between alkalinity and hardness. It is worth noting that none of these relationships show a significant positive or negative correlation; therefore, in the cases considered here, no variables were excluded for model development.

Based on the above, the IRCA modeling was conducted, aiming to validate which variables have the most influence based on their numerical terms, while also considering the perspective of the standard, with an analysis of the influence on the index from the assessment of compliance with various parameters. Although the IRCA in the data provided by the SDS shows a dependent variable with continuous Beta probability distribution function behaviors, since the IRCA presents systems with water quality "No Risk," i.e., at 0, the Beta function would not be applied directly but

Figure 3. Graphical analysis of the relationship between apparent color and pH, turbidity, iron, and manganese, with iron showing the strongest positive association

Figure 4. Graphical relationships between chlorides and conductivity, and between alkalinity and hardness, showing no significant correlations in the analyzed cases

rather a variant or special case, which would be the Beta Inflated at 0 (Stasinopoulos et al., 2008; Liu & Kong 2015).

Although the histogram shown in **Figure 5** does not exhibit typical Beta distribution behavior, it does show a zero-inflated behavior. Therefore, the modeling is conducted for two cases: one with zero inflation for all IRCA data and another with IRCA data that have a non-compliance rating with the standard (medium risk and above), i.e., greater than 14.1%.

The parameters that best model the water quality index, when expressed in its numerical results rather than its diagnosis, were determined. This analysis was conducted using the equation:

$$\text{Beta} \rightarrow \text{IRCA} = \text{Conductivity} + \text{pH} + \text{Turbidity} + \text{Color} + \text{Alkalinity} + \text{Chlorine} + \text{Chlorides} + \text{Phosphates} + \text{Manganese} + \text{Fluoride} + \text{Hardness} + \text{Iron} + \text{Mercury} + \text{Organophosphates} + \text{Lead}, \text{ generating the best model (considering the Bayesian Information Criterion - BIC)}$$

In the first scenario, the parameters that most influence the IRCA are conductivity, pH, apparent color, free residual chlorine, manganese, and hardness. In the second scenario, which considers IRCA values greater than or equal to 14.1%, the most influential parameters are conductivity, apparent color, alkalinity, chlorides, and hardness. Based on the statistical analysis of each parameter, an attempt is also made to spatially identify evidence of anthropogenic activities that may impact the system and subsequently affect the IRCA. In this initial case, two systems located in the Usme locality are examined. Near the water source, one can observe a cultivation area that might cause soil infiltration and affect water quality. One system, PP05001, is situated further away and upstream

Figure 5. Histogram of IRCA values showing a zero-inflated pattern, supporting modeling under two scenarios: the complete dataset and values $\geq 14.1\%$ corresponding to medium risk and higher

from the source, so it is unlikely that cultivation has any influence on its source. In contrast, for the system PP05002, the cultivation is upstream, or before the water reaches its intake, indicating a potential influence of the cultivation on the water quality, as evidenced in the georeferencing of **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. Location of two drinking water supply systems in Usme, showing the proximity of agricultural activities to the intake points and their potential influence on water quality

While there may be a spatial relationship, when the IRCA of the system is not met, the iron parameter in 2020 almost reached the compliance limit (0.30 mg/L). Phosphates, which are crucial for potato cultivation (Meier et al., 2022), although lacking data for the past two years, show a significant increase between 2020 and 2021, which might indicate a potential influence of cultivation on the water source. Although this does not lead to non-compliance with the standards, it may affect other parameters due to chemical reactions triggered by the presence of this compound. For instance, turbidity and apparent color consistently fail to meet the standards across all years, based on the averages of the studied systems, except for turbidity in 2020.

For the second case represented, system PP19005, located in the Ciudad Bolívar locality as shown in the georeferencing of **Figure 7**, there are two nearby cultivation areas close to the water source. This proximity suggests the potential for

infiltration or direct contamination of the source due to activities occurring within these plots. So, it's essential to strengthen drinking water treatment systems, consolidate rural aqueduct infrastructure, and ensure rigorous, systematic monitoring of water quality to guarantee its suitability for human consumption (Lora-Ariza et al., 2024). In parallel, continuous surveillance of morbidity and mortality indicators associated with waterborne exposure should be integrated into public health risk assessment frameworks.

Figure 7. Location of the PP19005 drinking water supply system in Ciudad Bolívar, showing nearby agricultural activities with potential influence on source water quality

Conclusions

The results indicate that rural potable water supply systems in Bogotá exhibit an average IRCA of 25.31%, corresponding to a medium health risk level, with no statistically relevant improvement in water quality throughout the analyzed period. This finding evidences the persistence of structural and operational limitations in rural water supply systems and underscores the need to strengthen continuous monitoring schemes, technical assistance, and interinstitutional coordination. Such measures are essential not only to improve data quality and analytical robustness, but also to support evidence-based decision-making aimed at reducing sanitary risk and ensuring the provision of safe drinking water for the rural population.

The comparative analysis between individual parameter behavior and the IRCA revealed limited concordance, with apparent color and iron being

the only parameters showing consistent alignment with index behavior. Despite this, the application of a zero-inflated Beta regression model proved to be an appropriate and robust methodological approach, allowing the identification of parameters with a statistically relevant influence on the IRCA under two analytical scenarios. In the first scenario, which considered the complete dataset, conductivity, pH, apparent color, free residual chlorine, manganese, and total hardness exhibited the strongest influence on the index. In the second scenario, restricted to IRCA values exceeding 14% (medium risk and higher), conductivity, apparent color, alkalinity, chlorides, and total hardness emerged as the most influential parameters.

The analysis clarified the relative contribution of individual physicochemical and toxicological parameters to the IRCA, providing technical evidence to support decision-making by water management and public health authorities in prioritizing monitoring, control, and mitigation actions. Additionally, the spatial analysis highlighted the potential influence of agricultural activities located near water catchment sources, underscoring the need for continuous evaluation of land-use practices, preventive management measures, and strengthened source protection strategies to reduce risks to drinking water quality.

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